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Professional Development Programmes towards Digitalisation Policy Implementation among Staff of Broadcast Media Organisations in Southwest, Nigeria

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Abstract

The rapid evolution of media technology has resulted into a large part of widespread use of contemporary digital technologies with the use of internet-connected devices which make production and sharing of information or content not only faster but world-wide delivered. Therefore, this study investigated professional development programme towards digitalisation policy implementation among staff of public and private-owned broadcast media organisations in Southwest, Nigeria. The study was anchored on Media Convergence and, Goal Setting Theory of Motivation. Descriptive survey research design was adopted and Sample included three hundred and sixty respondents selected through stratified and purposive sampling techniques selected from twelve radio and television stations located within Ogun, Oyo and Lagos States of Nigeria. A self-designed questionnaire named 'Digital Migration and Staff Development Questionnaire' (DiMigSDeQ) $r=0.87$ was used for data gathering. Findings revealed that staff of the broadcast station were regularly ($\bar{x}=2.18$) trained to update their skills and competences on digital technology skills; Respondents reported their participation in international training sponsored by the station towards digitalisation ($\bar{x} = 2.29$) and also majority were allowed to participate in professional digital trainings ($\bar{x} = 2.22$) as many times as possible within a year. Finding also revealed relatively positive perception of respondents on digitalisation policy implementation among private and public radio and television stations in Southwest Nigeria. Therefore, the study concludes that professional development programme and digitalisation policy implementation among private and public broadcast stations in

Southwest Nigeria is relatively on the average and moderately positive. Hence, the study recommends that private and public broadcast stations' media staff should be encouraged and permitted to attend more professional trainings, workshops, seminars and conferences as many times as possible to improve their digitalisation skills in the broadcast industry.

Keywords: Broadcast Stations, Digitalisation, Policy implementation, Professional development programmes

Word Count: 283

Introduction

The process of transforming information into digital binary language for computer use, whether it be through voice, text, sound, or image, is known as digitalisation (Chimang & Mumba 2020). Digitalisation is a technological process that makes it possible to convert and store data without worrying about it being lost or distorted in a machine language or computer readable format. All forms of mass communication, including telegraphy, photography, motion pictures, recorded music, and print media, are converting and transitioning from analogue to digital forms for easier access, storage, and future utilities. In Nigeria, digitalisation is more commonly associated with broadcast media. Converting and storing data and information into a string of binary digits is known as digitalisation. The author, further assert that digitalisation is the process of transferring analogue materials into digital format to increase accessibility and, if necessary, support preservation. Thus, digitalisation increases the capacity of communication channels, giving consumers more options, and opening up additional channels for interactive systems are all part of digitalisation. A technical process called "digitalisation" raises the caliber of information transfer.

The digitalisation capability is in line with the idea that digitalisation increases economic efficiency by improving audio and video transmission quality and saving time and labour by converting to digital forms for storage, retrieval, and editing. Digitalisation guarantees the preservation of primary data while representing images, audio, and video files as a sequence of integers (i.e., digital file size). Historically, Nigeria, broadcasting experience started with the Radio Diffusion Service in 1933 and Western Nigerian Television (WNTV) in October 1959 (Agbele, 2019). Until 2016, the main function of broadcasting was to transfer sound or video streams over the airwaves or cables using analogue signals. The issue of broadcast media digitalisation came to the forefront following the International Telecommunications Union (ITU) conferences in Senegal in 2004 and Geneva in 2006, where it was unanimously agreed that 2015 would be the deadline for the world to transition from analogue to digital broadcasting because of the fact that; broadcasting and digitalisation go hand in hand (Chimang & Mumba 2020).

Nigeria and many other African nations were granted an extension until 2020 to finish the transition. The following laid the foundation for the Geneva Agreement:

- i. To increase digital television transmission coverage;
- ii. To guarantee that there is enough bandwidth for wireless broadband services;
- iii. To improve the quality of the picture and sound, especially on high definition (HD) television;
- iv. To allow for more channels (more media material), and
- v. To allow unrestricted access to radio transmission via digital means

The phrase "switch-off" is always a common use when discussing the idea of digitalisation in the

broadcasting industry; this relies on the perception that signals the end of terrestrial broadcasting via the analogue system and the transition to digital broadcasting via cable, DSL (Digital Subscriber Lines), satellite, and terrestrial media. It's a system used in the media industry to process, transform, and synchronize communication that are presented as text, speech, image, or sound into "digital binary language for computer use." Additionally, it includes "computer, telecommunication, audio and visual, and consumer electrical and electronic gadgets" in its list of covered devices. Digital television comes in three flavours: satellite DTV, cable DTV, and terrestrial DTV (Agbele, 2019). Digitalisation is more of a change or advancement in technology than a brand-new occurrence. Mobile phones, laptops, and desktop computers are examples of devices that have undergone digitalisation. The author asserts that Nigeria needs to switch from terrestrial to digital broadcasting, as has been emphasized (Agbele, 2019).

Expectedly, viewers will switch from free Ultra High Frequency (UHF) and Very High Frequency (VHF) programming to pay-as-you-watch channels on broadband wireless technology, which offers instantaneous production, storage, and distribution along with high-quality digital signals. Digital broadcasting is such data, which contain audio and visual signals, can be distributed via cable distribution networks, satellite broadcast transponders, or terrestrial transmitters using conventional wireless media. In addition to being sluggish and awkward, the analogue age of broadcasting had a restricted reach, there was no way to access the Internet, and the visual quality was low. The global phenomena of technological growth have redefined mass communication and shaped broadcasting. Scientific and technological advancements have expanded broadcasting's speed, dispersion, and transmission reach while also improving its flexibility (Agbele, 2019).

Compared to analogue broadcasting, digital broadcasting offers many benefits. The broadcaster and the public can benefit much from the digital revolution. These benefits could include a variety of channels, high-quality signals, media convergence, and programming content.

Agbele (2019) through the following assertion highlights the benefits and advantages of digitalization:

- i. Advertisers looking to reach consumers, prospects, and the advertising industry at large will have a plethora of new chances as television moves from the traditional television set to mobile devices. Stated differently, the availability of several channels for consumer outreach implies that digitalization offers a favourable platform for advertisers to promote their offerings.
- ii. Due to the fact that digital broadcasting is more responsive, has a larger coverage area, and is more efficient than traditional media, audiences will see and hear shows with greater clarity and quality. Additionally, viewers can utilise the smart television set in connection with other communication devices, including a computer and a phone, and receive several channels from a single station.
- iii. Digitalisation makes it possible to transmit audio and visuals of theatre quality over satellite, cable, or antenna. Additionally, it supports multicasting, which enables the delivery of several programmes over a single digital audio stream.
- iv. As a result of existing broadcast stations starting to add more channels to better suit the interests of their audiences, digitalisation leads to an increase in demand for programmes.

Since a radio or television station can stream or broadcast more programmes on several channels while using the same frequency, digital broadcasting ushers in a new era of cost effectiveness for broadcasters. Since only a small number of humans, or personnel, are needed to operate these devices using digital technology, less money will be spent on infrastructure, maintenance, and operation.

vi. Since NBC receives more money from new licenses, digitalisation safeguard the interests of regulators

by encouraging the growth of specialist broadcasting, which target regions that commercial broadcasters usually ignore.

Moreover, development is typically used to refer to a broader scope than "learning" or "training," all of which may be included in the notion of development. It can refer to a wide range of activities, including coaching and more formal educational commitments and experiences. In order to carry out their responsibilities successfully and efficiently, managerial staff must acquire and apply information, skills, attitudes, and insights through development, a practical study and development exercise. For managerial personnel to handle the complexity of organisational and technological developments, it is essential. Their recognition of their social and societal responsibilities is another benefit of the training. Staff development can boost employees' sense of self-fulfillment, revitalise their work capacity, and better equip them to take on and overcome new challenges (Shuibin, Benjamin & Naam 2020).

Consequently, in order to guarantee that staff members keep getting better, training and development must be combined. In addition to reducing personnel obsolescence which can be brought on by age, attitude, or a person's incapacity to adjust to technology changes, training and development foster employee initiative and creativity. While training and staff development are focused on present employment, development is more concerned with possible future employment. In essence, training and development are meant to support the organization's overarching objective (Shuibin, Benjamin & Naam 2020). The justification for staff development stems from the expanding organisational scope and evolving business practices, which have strongly emphasised the value of training and development in converting human resources into human capital and fostering a culture of collaboration, creativity, and ongoing learning in the workplace. Human capital refers to the workforce reforms proposed by Garry Becker, which involve investing in employee training and development to enhance the organization's human capital. The concept is similar in that training and development enable organisations to retain a pool of workers for future promotions and replacements. Contributing to the organization's ultimate objective is essentially the aim of training and development (Mohammed, Mohammed & Gana 2022).

Employees' progression and change management abilities are fostered via training and development, which gives them the confidence to replace and promote staff members. In a similar vein, it has been suggested that procedures related to training and development be pushed by emphasising the advantages in terms of enhanced competencies immersed in employees, thereby altering their work behavior. Training will become more and more crucial since only in an atmosphere that fosters lifelong learning can organisational excellence be guaranteed. The mission and goal of an organisation must include training and development. Numerous research studies have been carried out to investigate the advantages of employee training with respect to enhanced organisational productivity (Owolabi & Amisu, 2019). There is no doubt that the goal of training and development is to raise performance levels at work. Another study reported that, a lot of well-known companies invest a lot of money in employee training and development (Mohammed, Mohammed & Gana 2022).

A balanced scorecard evaluates an organization's productivity from four angles: its financial situation; the services and contentment it offers to its clients; its internal and external business processes; and its growth and learning opportunities for both employees and the company. Consequently, the availability of

opportunities for training and development is one of the indicators used to measure the growth and success of an organisation. Companies do not often take into account how their staff members feel about developing their skills. Because militaries are the biggest and most likely the oldest human organisations, traditional corporate organisations are heavily influenced by military management practices (Mohammed, Mohammed, & Gana 2022). Thus, some of the reasons why employers mandate that their staff members acquire new skills on a regular basis are as follows:

- i. **Capital Enhancement:** Businesses invest heavily in modernising their buildings and machinery, but they spend very little on improving their human capital. Although workers are a company's greatest asset, employers prioritise making ends meet and maximising profits over training staff members, which may hinder productivity. Even if the company is productive, staff loyalty, commitment, and dedication should also be highlighted. Employees without continuous training will not make the best use of modern equipment.
- ii. **Morale Boost:** Workers will be more productive if they consistently enhance their job skills. Employee skill development is crucial in the outside world as well as the workplace. Happy employees may be productive, but more productive employees are happier since it advances both the socioeconomic development of each individual worker and the country as a whole.
- iii. **Ability to Adapt to Change:** The workforce's level of expertise will determine how easily the company as a whole can adjust to shifts in the demand for its goods and services both domestically and internationally. Because of the uncertainty that comes with change, employees can be unwilling to adjust.

Theoretically, the study is anchored on three theories namely Media Convergence Theory and Goal Setting Theory of Motivation.

1. Media Convergence Theory: Digital media refers to any format or device that uses digital signals to convey material, including text, audio, video, and images. Digitalized content can be delivered over computer networks or the Internet. This also includes newspaper, magazine, and television news that is posted on a website or blog (Nadaf, 2019). Media encoded in machine-readable forms are referred to as digital media. Software, digital photos, videos, web pages, websites, social media, digital data, digital music, and electronic books are examples of digital media that can be created, viewed, shared, altered, and presented on digital electronic devices. Products and services from the media, entertainment, and information industries, as well as their subsectors, can also be included in this definition. It consists of digital platforms that can be accessed and used by various digital devices, including text, audio, video, photos, and services. Digital media, however, are also communication technologies that support and enable user-to-user and user-information interaction. Nadaf (2019) postulate that users of digital media benefit from a sense of community and relationship-building, despite geographical and temporal limitations, digital media are always being redefined and altered by the interplay of new technologies, shifting cultural norms, mass creativity, and other variables.

In order to continue processing and disseminating news, traditional media companies are investigating and embracing digital media. "Media convergence" is the term that arose from traditional media operators' adoption of digital media. Media convergence refers to the amalgamation of conventional and digital media over the Internet, in conjunction with highly interactive and portable technology via digital media platforms. The following are the most well-known instances of media convergence: (1) smart phones combining all other media with their cameras, music, books, the Internet, and other devices; (2) Online radio, which combines radio and the Internet; (3) e-books, which combines digital technology with paperbacks; and (4) news

websites and applications. Nadaf (2019) infer again that the convergence of disparate means and equipment for the creation and dissemination of media content is the definition given by the proponent of the Media Convergence theory. It was stated that media convergence must be understood from the perspective of social as well as technological revolutions within human civilization, since media audiences nowadays are the content producers and distributors. One of media convergence's primary and most important features is the interconnectivity of different media formats.

Media convergence was understood to be the "cooperation and collaboration" of many, previously unconnected media formats. Media convergence has blurred the boundaries between various media forms and assimilated them in distinctive digital forms that are universally accessible to all the existing types of audience and this was the reason why media convergence was also defined as the blending of media, telecommunications and computer industries. Nadaf (2019) further noted that under rapid convergence which is happening in the contemporary media sector, many media formats namely; television, print, radio, and on-line media sources are aided by portable and interactive digital technology. Technological and economic media convergences are the two main vantage points on this phenomenon. One of the main factors influencing media convergence is the development of media technology and the various ways that news is disseminated over communication networks in the media sector.

Consequently, the media industry is experiencing a convergence because of the development of digital technology, which has resulted in a fusion of computer networking and digitalisation that has gone beyond the limits of the conventional division of media forms. Instantaneous and quick news information exchanges have occurred worldwide as a result of the integration of old and new media. The 1990s saw a proliferation of Internet networks, which in turn sped up global media industry convergence. The democratisation of media brought about by media convergence and the development of digital technology has made it possible for the average Internet user to create and share media material in addition to having access to digital media via computer networks. Furthermore, because content creators no longer have exclusive control over information distribution, media convergence has clearly changed how journalism is conducted in the media industry. This is due to the fact that people who were formerly referred to as "media consumers" are now also "media producers" and "communicators" thanks to digital technology. Users may now create material and combine their responsibilities as media producers thanks to digital technologies. The development of media material has experienced an expansion, acceleration, and facilitation of distribution and dissemination due to technological convergence (Nadaf, 2019).

The relevance of this theory is that the theory describes what happens in many broadcast media in Nigeria during this period when smooth transition is taking place from analogue to digital broadcasting equipment and this has made content production and broadcasting to done easily and seamlessly and it has also resulted into many media consumers or audiences becoming media content producers and transmitters. Media Convergence has also resulted into broadcast media like television and radio going borderless, that is, the ability of radio to possess the characteristics of being both audio and visual like television and also the ability of the two media to make use of social media platforms as channels through which contents are shared.

2. Goal Setting Theory of Motivation: The goal-setting theory of motivation was proposed by Edwin Locke

in the 1960s, and it holds that task performance and goal-setting are fundamentally related. It claims that more precise and difficult goals combined with relevant feedback lead to improved task performance. To promote behaviour change, public groups and government agencies propose goal setting as one of the key ways. A goal is defined as the intent or purpose of an action. Setting goals is a crucial part of helping people control their conduct, and it's been applied in a number of areas, including social behaviours, health, and education. Establishing goals is a common behaviour change strategy, the fundamental tenet of Locke is that a person acts according to his or her conscious intentions, and a goal is just what a person is consciously trying to do. Therefore, challenging goals beat simple ones, and specific, challenging goals beat having no goals or the overarching goal of "do your best." Thus, because they focus attention, mobilise effort, and encourage persistence and plan design, goals are associated with greater performance. Setting goals is a subject that has gained a lot of attention lately. For good cause, too; according to the research, goal-setting can boost output and performance by 11 to 25%. Increasing productivity and performance is a great benefit of this strategy. Regretfully, despite how simple this idea seems, there is actually some complexity involved.

Furthermore, studies showed that not all objectives are the same or appropriate for every circumstance, and that, most significantly, setting the incorrect objective in the wrong circumstance can have a negative impact on performance and even lower productivity. (Locke & Latham 2019). It has been demonstrated that goal-setting therapies utilising Goal Setting Theory (GST) improve task-related performance, and it is hypothesised that this impact takes place via four mechanisms. First, goal setting instructs people to avoid unrelated activities and concentrate their energies on goal-related tasks. Second, creating goals gives people energy and motivates them to work towards achieving them. Third, persistence is influenced by goals; harder goals require more work to achieve. Lastly, aiming for goals makes it easier to find and create solutions that are relevant to the task at hand. The second core tenet of GST is that five goal attributes which are goal difficulty, goal specificity, goal proximity, goal source, and goal types are directly influencing the impact of goal setting (Locke & Latham 2019).

The following are some of the benefits and drawbacks of goal setting theory: The goal setting hypothesis is a tactic used to increase employee incentives for finishing tasks efficiently and on time. Establishing goals improves performance by boosting motivation and effort as well as by raising and enhancing the calibre of feedback. The primary drawback, though, is that occasionally, managerial and organisational objectives diverge. When goal conflict drives incompatible action drift, it negatively impacts performance. Goals that are extremely complex and challenging encourage risky behaviour. Setting goals can be unsuccessful and compromise performance if the individual has the abilities and competencies to carry out the tasks necessary to achieve them. There's no data to support the claim that having goals increases job satisfaction. (Locke & Latham 2019). The relevance of Goal Setting Theory to this study is that goal which may be development training when approached with commitment, orientation and motivation, such goals will be achieved and productive. In this regard, goals should be well accepted and adopted by the workforce so that the improved and reimbursed goal/result would be used in carrying out the organisation's job efficiently and efficiently. If the employee lacks skills and competencies to perform actions essential for goal, then the goal-setting can fail and lead to undermining of performance which inadvertently means that if an organisation's goals are not imbibed and accepted by the workers, then the organisation may not be able to realize some of its policies and missions.

Aim and Objectives of the study

The aim of the study is to investigate perception of staff on the implementation of the digitalization policy and exposure to professional development programmes among selected public and private-owned broadcast media organisations in Southwest, Nigeria. The objectives are to:

1. ascertain the extent exposure to professional development programmes among staff of public and private-owned broadcast media organisations in Southwest, Nigeria.
2. ascertain the perception of staff on exposure to professional development programmes geared towards digitalisation policy implementation among public and private-owned broadcast media organisations in Southwest, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following questions were answered:

1. What is the extent of staff exposure to professional development programmes among public and private-owned broadcast media organisations in Southwest, Nigeria?
2. What is the perception of staff on exposure to professional development programmes geared towards digitalisation policy implementation among public and private-owned broadcast media organisations in Southwest, Nigeria?

Radio and television broadcasting organisations in Nigeria are somehow still resistant to technical advancement and unconcerned with the reality of contemporary broadcasting innovations especially in the developed countries. This is because radio and television broadcasting in the twenty-first century are dependent on a number of technological indicators especially given the accelerating rate of growth that is characterised by digitalisation. It is however noticed that Nigeria's progress on the global digitalisation train, which is accelerating media development, has been perceived to be slow. In essence, it is critical to assess how Nigerian media, particularly radio and television, use digitalisation potential as tools to compete effectively with other international media, this is because when broadcast organisation have look-warm attitude and did not embrace digitalisation holistically, programme or content production and distribution of such station is affected. This implies that the station may not be able to explore technological creativity in its production and operations which will have negative effects on such a station to the extent of the station not being patronized and followed. It is unimagined that there will be a broadcast station in this age that will not make use of social media or platforms to create and disseminate information or contents. While it is evident that such a station is lagging behind in digitalisation, such a station may not survive. Therefore, this study investigates professional development programmes towards digitalisation policy implementation among staff of public and private-owned broadcast media organisations in Southwest, Nigeria

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design with population includes Nine and Hundred and Sixty (960) media personnel working in twelve radio and television stations namely: Premier FM, Lead City FM, Nigerian Television Authority (N.T.A.), and Impact Television in Oyo State; Eko FM, Cool FM, Lagos State Television (L.T.V), Murhi International Television (M.I.T.V) and African Independent Television (A.I.T) in Lagos State; and Ogun State Broadcasting Corporation (O.G.B.C), Splash FM and Ogun State Television (O.G.T.V) in Ogun State. Sample included three hundred and sixty (360) with the use of stratified and purposive sampling techniques. The research instrument was a self designed questionnaire named Digital

Migration and Staff Development Questionnaire (DiMigSDeQ). Data collected were analysed with Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software and results were presented in simple frequency and percentages. Table 1 presents the respondents distribution by ownership, status gender, qualification and work experience.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents' Demographic Information (N = 360)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Type of Ownership of Broadcast Station		
Public (Federal or State)	268	74.0
Private	94	26.0
Designation & Status		
Junior Staff	149	41.0
Technical Staff	62	17.0
Senior staff	103	29.0
Management Staff	48	13.0
Gender		
Male	199	55.0
Female	163	45.0
Qualification		
SSCE/WASCE	41	11.3
ND	39	10.7
HND	92	25.0
Degree	123	34.0
Master's Degree	67	19.0
Years of Working with the Station		
1-5 Years	137	38.0
6-10 Years	67	19.0
11-15 Years	56	16.0
16-20 Years	31	9.0
21-25 Years	23	6.0
26-30 Years	36	9.0
31-35 Years	12	3.0

Source: Field Survey 2023

Table 1 revealed the summary of respondents' demographic data in terms of type of ownership of Broadcast station, designation, sex, qualification and years of working with the stations. From table 1 it was observed that 74% of the study respondents were working in Public (Federal or State-owned broadcast stations) while 26% of the respondents were working in private owned broadcast stations. The result implied that there were more individuals working with public (Federal or State-owned broadcast stations) who participated in the study compared to their counterpart, working in private owned broadcast stations.

Table 1 presents the designation of the sampled respondents and it was discovered that 41% of the study respondents were junior staff, 17% of the study respondents were technical staff, 29% of them were senior staff and 13% of the respondents were management staff. The result implied that there were more junior

staff who participated in the study, followed by senior and technical staff respectively.

Besides, Table 1 showed the sex distribution of the respondents. It was observed that 55% of the study respondents were male while 45% were female. The result implied that there were more male who participated in the study compare to their female counterparts. Also, it can be observed from Table 1 that 11% of the study respondents were SSCE/WASCE holders, 11% of the study respondents were ND holders, 25% of the study respondents were HND holders, 34% were Degree holders and 19% of the respondents were Master's Degree holders. The result implied that majority of the study respondents were holders of Higher National Diploma qualifications that have exposed them to various experiences to supply information needed in this study.

Furthermore, Table 1 revealed the summary of respondents' years of working with their various stations, it was observed that, 38% of the study respondents were 1-5 years of working with their stations, 19% of the respondents were 6-10 years of working with their stations, 16% of the respondents were 11-15 years of working with their stations 9% of the study respondents were 16-20 years of working with their stations, 6% of the respondents were 21-25 years of working with their stations, 9% were of 26-30 years of working with their stations and 3% of the respondents were 31-35 years of working with their stations. Deducing from the findings, it was obvious that majority of the study respondents have less years of working with their stations, as the findings revealed more respondents in 1-5 years of working with their stations, followed by respondents who were within 6-10 years of working with their stations. Further implication of this result is that the sampled were qualified enough to supply the necessary information needed in this study.

Data Analysis and Results

Research Question One: What is the extent of staff exposure to professional development programmes among public and private-owned broadcast media organisations in Southwest, Nigeria?

Table 2. Extent of Exposure to Professional Development Programme among Private and Public Radio and Television Stations (N=360)

S/N	Digital Migration Statements	SA	A	SD	D	Mean	SD
1.	Members of staff are trained by the station on new innovations in the industry from time to time in preparation for digital migration	43 (12%)	62 (17%)	94 (26%)	163 (45%)	1.96	1.05
2.	Workshops and tutorials are organised for members of staff from time to time to equip them for digital migration	46 (13%)	79 (22%)	122 (34%)	115 (41%)	2.15	1.01
3.	Members of staff are permitted to pursue further professional trainings in relation to digitalisation technology	52 (14%)	42 (12%)	93 (26%)	175 (48%)	1.92	1.08
4.	The station trains her workforce regularly to get updated skills and competences on digital technology skills	50 (14%)	78 (22%)	121 (33%)	113 (31%)	2.18	1.03
5.	Funds are made available to members	56	88	120	98	2.28	1.03

	of staff for training towards the digital switch	(16%)	(24%)	(33%)	(27%)		
6.	Members of staff are involved in in-house digital technology trainings in my organization	48 (13%)	64 (18%)	121 (33%)	129 (36%)	2.09	1.03
7.	Workers in this station participated in international training sponsored by the station towards digitalization	60 (17%)	87 (24%)	112 (31%)	103 (29%)	2.29	1.05
8.	Members of staff are allowed to participate in professional and digital trainings as at when due		82 (23%)	177 (32%)	109 (30%)	2.22	1.04

Source: Field Survey 2023

Key: SA= Strongly Agree, A=Agree, SD = Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree

Table 2 showed perception of staff on digitalisation policy implementation among private and public broadcast stations in Southwest Nigeria, to answer this research question, a weighted mean 2.17 of the eight items was determined and taken as a benchmark for decision making and inference. Finding revealed that some of the items buttressed the fact that perception of staff on digitalisation policy implementation among private and public broadcast stations in Southwest Nigeria is on the average as 4 out of the 8 items used to capture perception of staff on digitalisation policy implementation among private and public radio and television stations are having means above the set benchmark of 2.17.

For instance, on the item which stated that: The station trains her workforce regularly to get updated skills and competences on digital technology skills ($\bar{x} = 2.18$), Funds are made available to members of staff for training towards the digital switch ($\bar{x} = 2.28$), Workers in this station participated in international training sponsored by the station towards digitalisation ($\bar{x} = 2.29$) and members of staff in this station are allowed to participate in professional digital trainings as many times as possible within a year ($\bar{x} = 2.22$) reinforced the perception of staff on digitalisation policy implementations among private and public radio and television stations.

In summary, finding on research question one revealed that staff exposure to professional development programmes among private and public Radio and Television Stations in Southwest Nigeria is relatively on average.

Research Question Two: What is the perception of staff on exposure to professional development programmes geared towards digitalisation policy implementation among public and private-owned broadcast media organisations in Southwest, Nigeria?

Table 3. Perception of Staff on Exposure to Professional Development towards Digitalisation Policy Implementation among Private and Public Radio and Television Stations (N=360)

S/N	Digital Migration Statements	SA	A	SD	D	Mean	SD
1.	Members of staff have participated in national training on digital media professionalism	37 (10%)	79 (22%)	132 (37%)	114 (31%)	2.11	0.97
2.	There are restrictions to number of	61	77	120	104	2.26	1.05

	times a staff is allowed to go for professional training in a year	(17%)	(21%)	(33%)	(29%)		
3.	It is mandatory for members of staff in this station to attend professional digital training once in a year	71	92	99	100	2.37	1.09
		(20%)	(25%)	(27%)	(28%)		
4.	Trainings attended by staff in this station usually result into promotional or economic benefits	68	100	106	88	2.41	1.05
		(19%)	(28%)	(29%)	(24%)		
5.	A staff that has not participated in any training within the past two or three years may not be promoted in this station	65	95	103	99	2.35	1.07
		(18%)	(26%)	(29%)	(27%)		
6.	Members of staff are more productive as a result of staff professional development training attended in the past	38	76	121	127	2.07	0.99
		(10%)	(21%)	(33%)	(35%)		
7.	Members of staff who have benefitted from professional training sponsored by the employers are loyal to such organizations	43	72	124	123	2.10	1.00
		(12%)	(20%)	(34%)	(34%)		
8.	Members of staff in this station are committed to their jobs because they are exposed to professional on -the-job training opportunities	38	60	97	167	1.91	1.02
		(11%)	(17%)	(27%)	(46%)		
Weighted Mean						2.17	1.35

Source: Field Survey 2023

Key: SA= Strongly Agree, A=Agree, SD = Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree

Table 3 showed Professional Development among Private and Public Radio and Television Stations in Southwest Nigeria, to answer this research question, a weighted mean (2.17) of the eight items was determined and taken as a benchmark for decision making and inference. The table revealed that some of the items buttressed the Professional Development among Private and Public Radio and Television stations in Southwest Nigeria is on the average as 5 out of the 9 items used to capture professional development among private and public radio and television stations are having means above the set benchmark of 2.17. For instance, on the item which stated that: Members of staff in this station are allowed to participate in professional digital trainings as many times as possible within a year ($\bar{x} = 2.21$), there are restrictions to number of times a staff is allowed to go for professional training in a year ($\bar{x} = 2.26$), It is mandatory for members of staff in this station to attend specialized digital training once in a year ($\bar{x} = 2.37$), Trainings attended by staff in this station usually result into promotional or economic benefits ($\bar{x} = 2.41$), A staff that has not participated in any training within the past two or three years may not be promoted in this station ($\bar{x} = 2.35$) established the need for professional development among private and public Radio and Television stations However, items (1, 7, 8 and 9 (\bar{x}) means respectively) were below the set bench mark. In summary, finding on research question two regarding the perception of staff on their exposure to

professional development programmes geared towards digitalisation policy implementation among public and private-owned broadcast media organisations in Southwest, Nigeria. Finding revealed that media staff exposure is relatively on the average.

Discussion of Findings

Finding on research question one with regards to extent of exposure of staff to professional development programmes among public and private broadcast stations in Southwest Nigeria is that staff development training programmes for the sampled respondents were averagely available and the development training programme were: professional workshop attendance, professional conference attendance within state, professional conference attendance within the country and seminar attendance. This indicated the extent of exposure of staff to professional development programmes is above average level. This is evident in that respondents used in this study indicated that they have access to more than average of the factors presented to them. In other words, respondents indicated majority of the training programmes as being accessible to them from where they had been trained about digital migration which had equipped them to be digital compliant or be able to operate digital equipment in broadcast industries. By indication also, this means staff in broadcast stations know about digital migration and the need to be trained in other to operate or work in digital broadcast stations. For instance, on the item which stated that: Members of staff in this station are allowed to participate in professional digital trainings as many times as possible within a year ($\bar{x}\bar{x} = 2.21$), there are restrictions to number of times a staff is allowed to go for professional training in a year ($\bar{x}\bar{x} = 2.26$), It is mandatory for members of staff in this station to attend specialized digital training once in a year ($\bar{x}\bar{x} = 2.37$), Trainings attended by staff in this station usually result into promotional or economic benefits ($\bar{x}\bar{x} = 2.41$), A staff that has not participated in any training within the past two or three years may not be promoted in this station ($\bar{x}\bar{x} = 2.35$) established the need for professional development among private and public Radio and Television stations

Invariably, the finding on research question one buttressed the fact that training and development are crucial tactical tools for effective personality and organisational performance, thus, organisations continue to invest hugely in training and re-training of its workers in order to achieve stated goals and objectives. While organisations want to achieve the primary aim of maximising profits as well as ensuring that aims and objectives of an organisation is achieved, it is expected of organisations to determine the training needs of their staff and create programmes that guarantee the achievement of the objectives (Mohammed, Mohammed & Gana, 2022). Furthermore, finding of research question two revealed the perception of staff on exposure to professional development programmes geared towards digitalisation policy implementation among public and private-owned broadcast media organisations in Southwest, Nigeria; which was moderately positive. The finding revealed that some of the responses to the items buttressed the fact that perception of staff on digitalisation policy implementation indicated that the sampled broadcast stations were involved in training their workforce regularly to get updated skills and competences on digital

technology skills ($\bar{x} = 2.18$), also, funds are made available to members of staff for training towards the digital switch ($\bar{x} = 2.28$), Workers in this station participated in international training sponsored by the station towards digitalisation ($\bar{x} = 2.29$) and respondents as members of staff in the sampled broadcast stations are allowed to participate in the required digital trainings as many times as possible within a year ($\bar{x} = 2.22$) which reinforced the positive perception of staff on digitalisation policy implementation among private and public Radio and Television broadcast stations. The implication of the finding is that an average staff of broadcast industry knows about digitalisation and is aware of the policy and professional training required for a broadcast station to be digitalised.

Moreover, the broadcast stations made funds available to staff members to enhance their knowledge and digital equipment operational skills towards the attainment of higher service delivery and better task performance; as corroborated by Goal-setting theory's salient aspects include; the primary source of job motivation is the willingness to work towards achieving goals (Locke & Latham 2019). Hence, better performance and higher productivity are the results of having clear and defined goals and trainings. When an employee has been exposed to enough training and professional development, it fills him with joy and triumph and prepares him to work harder and productively to achieve the organisation's target as well as reach the next objective. Better and more relevant feedback on performance also influences employee behaviour and raises performance levels compared to when it is absent. Gaining reputation, providing clarifications, and managing goal challenges are all accomplished through feedback. It encourages increased involvement from workers and increases job satisfaction. (Locke & Latham 2019).

This finding is also in accordance with a study on the impact of employee development on organisational performance (Owolabi & Amisu, 2019). Findings from the study showed that organisational performance is significantly impacted by staff development and that regular staff development is necessary for career growth and greater employee loyalty which improve work performance and productivity. The study postulated that overall staff performance will boost the effectiveness of the organisation. The assumption is that having well-trained employees will improve organisational performance since they will produce more effectively and efficiently, which will raise overall performance of the organization (Owolabi & Amisu, 2019).

Conclusion

Arising from the findings, it can be concluded that staff exposure to professional development programmes towards digitalisation policy implementation among public and private-owned broadcast media organisations in Southwest, Nigeria is relatively on the average and moderately positive. The implication is that an average media staff within the broadcast industry among public and private-owned broadcast media organisations in Southwest, Nigeria knows about digitalisation policy. This is as a result of their exposure to professional development training. This is evident in that majority of the respondents indicated accessibility to training programmes in relation to digital migration; which invariably, had equipped them to be digital compliant through their ability to operate digital equipment within the broadcast stations covered in this study.

Recommendations

1. Members of staff of broadcast stations should be regularly trained on digital skills and digitalisation in order to be fully equipped for digital migration of broadcast stations to enhance productivity of all cadres of staff.
2. Members of staff of broadcast stations should be encouraged and permitted to attend professional trainings, workshops, seminars and conferences as many times as possible to improve their perception and acceptance of digitalisation of broadcast industries.

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